

University of Nebraska - Lincoln

DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska - Lincoln

Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

Libraries at University of Nebraska-Lincoln

July 2021

Load Flow Solution of Distribution Systems - A Bibliometric Survey

K. V. S. Ramachandra Murthy

Aditya Engineering College, Surampalem, murthy.kvs@aec.edu.in

Vijay Kumar D

Aditya Institute of Technology and Management, Tekkali, drdvk2010@gmail.com

Lakshmi Kambhampati

Aditya College of Engineering, Surampalem, lakshmi_eee@acoee.edu.in

Rayudu Srinivas

Aditya College of Engineering and Technology, Surampalem, srinivas.r@acet.ac.in

Rayudu Srinivas

Aditya Engineering College, Surampalem, dean_sb@aec.edu.in

Follow this and additional works at: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac>

Part of the [Electrical and Electronics Commons](#), and the [Library and Information Science Commons](#)

Murthy, K. V. S. Ramachandra; D, Vijay Kumar; Kambhampati, Lakshmi; Srinivas, Rayudu; and Srinivas, Rayudu, "Load Flow Solution of Distribution Systems - A Bibliometric Survey" (2021). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 5812.

<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5812>

Load Flow Solution of Distribution Systems - A Bibliometric Survey

K V S Ramachandra Murthy

Aditya Engineering College, Surampalem, India

D. Vijay Kumar

Aditya Institute of Technology and Management, Tekkali, India

Lakshmi Kambhampati,

Aditya College of Engineering, Surampalem, India

Rayudu Srinivas, *EEE Department*

Aditya College of Engineering and Technology, Surampalem, India

Rayudu Srinivas, *CSE Department*

Aditya Engineering College, Surampalem, India

ABSTRACT

In this paper, Bibliometric Survey has been carried out on ‘Load Flow Solution of Distribution Systems’ from 2012 to 2021. Scopus database has been used for the analysis. There were total 1711 documents found on this topic. The statistical analysis is carried out source wise, year wise, area wise, Country wise, University wise, author wise, and based on funding agency. Network analysis is also carried out based on Co-authorship, Co-occurrence. Results are presented. During 2020 and 2018, there were 263 documents published which is the highest. ‘IEEE Transactions on Power Systems’ has published 90 documents during the period of study which is the highest in terms of articles under the category of sources. Highest citations were received by the article authored by Hung and Mithulanathan with 484 citations in the collected database with the chosen key words. VOSviewer 1.6.16 is the software that is used for the statistical analysis and network analysis on the database. It provides a very effective way to analyze the co-authorship, co-occurrences, citation and bibliometric analysis etc. The Source for all Tables and figures is www.scopus.com, The data is assessed on 6th July, 2021.

Key Words : Load flow solution, Distribution System, load flow analysis, Bibliometric Analysis, statistical analysis, network analysis.